

Research Article

Polyherbal Gel Formulation For Treatment Of Gout

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01 July 2024

Accepted: 03 July 2024

Published: 05 Aug 2024

Keywords:

Gout, Neurological disorder,
Hyperuricaemia,
Osteoporosis, Flaxseeds oil.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13220470

ABSTRACT

Flaxseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L) is an ancient perennial plant species regarded as a multipurpose plant owing to its richness in omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) including α -linolenic acid (ALA). The extensive biochemical analysis of flaxseed resulted in the identification of its bioactive, i.e., lignans with potential application in the improvement of human health. Flaxseed oil, fibers, and lignans exert potential health benefits including reduction of cardiovascular disease, atherosclerosis, diabetes, cancer, arthritis, osteoporosis, and autoimmune and neurological disorders that have led to the diversification of flaxseed plant applications. This comprehensive review focuses on flaxseed oil as the major product of flaxseed with emphasis on the interrelationship between its chemical composition and biological effects. Effects reviewed include antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anticancer, antiulcer, anti-osteoporotic, cardioprotective, metabolic, and neuroprotective. This study provides an overview of flaxseed oil effects with the reported action mechanisms related to its phytochemical composition and in comparison, to other PUFA-rich oils. This study presents the most updated and comprehensive review summarizing flaxseed oil's health benefits for the treatment of various diseases. Gout is a chronic disease caused by monosodium urate (MSU) crystal deposition. Gout typically presents as an acute, self-limiting inflammatory monoarthritis that affects the joints of the lower limb. Elevated serum urate level (hyperuricaemia) is the major risk factor for MSU crystal deposition and development of gout. Although traditionally considered a disorder of purine metabolism, altered urate transport, both in the gut and the kidneys, has a key role in the pathogenesis of hyperuricaemia.

INTRODUCTION

Flaxseed (*Linum usitatissimum*) is also known as linseed and these terms are used interchangeably. Flaxseed is often used to describe flax when consumed by humans while

linseed denotes when it is used specifically for industrial applications. It is popularly known as Alsi, Jawas, Aksebija in Indian languages. The Latin name of the flaxseed is *Linum usitatissimum*, which means "very useful". Flaxseed was first

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

introduced in United States by Colonists, primarily to produce fiber for clothing. Flaxseed was used for the fabrication of cloths and papers, while flaxseed oil and its sub-products are used in animal feed formulation. Flaxseeds are obtained from blue flowering annual herb and belong to Linaceae family. Flax plants grow from 12 to 40 inches high. The plant has a slender and fibrous stem and its bright blue flowers are up to 3 cm in diameter. The flowers have five petals and form a five-celled ball that can contain up to 10 seeds. Flowering continues until plant growth stops. The spherical fruit capsules contain two seeds in each of five compartments. Fiber flax varieties are tall, unbranched plants that are grown at very high density to maximize fiber production. The whole flaxseed is flat and oval with pointed tips and contains a seed coat or true hull (also called testa), a thin endosperm, two embryos and an embryo axis. It have smooth glossy surface. It varies in color from dark brown to yellow. The texture of flaxseed is crisp and chewy possessing a pleasant nutty taste. Distinct varieties namely Sheela, Sweta, Garima, Sharda, Rashmi, Shikha, Padmini, Shekhar, Neelam, LC-2063 and LC-2023 are cultivated in India have been developed for oilseed and fiber flax.

Table No.1: Taxonomical classification of *L. usitatissimum*

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Malpighi ales
Family	Linaceae
Genus	Linum
Species	<i>L.usitatissimum</i>

Oilseed flax varieties tend to be short, highly branched plants bred to maximize the number of flowers per unit area. India ranks first among the leading flaxseed producing countries in terms of acreage accounting 23.8 % of the total and third in production contributing to 10.2 % of the world's

production. In India, it is mainly cultivated in Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Chhattisgarh and Bihar. Almost all parts of linseed plant are utilized for various purposes. Seed contains oil which after refining is used for edible purpose. It has been used in various forms such as flour, oil and seed. Flaxseed and flaxseed oil is considered to have potential health benefits due to presence of various biologically active compounds and elements including linolenic acid, linoleic acid, lignans, cyclic peptides, polysaccharides, alkaloids, cyanogenic glycosides, and cadmium. It relishes a good status among oilseeds because of its versatile uses. It has emerged as a captivating nutritional food because of its exceptionally high content of alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), dietary fiber, high quality protein and phytoestrogens. In the last two decades, flaxseed has been the grabbing the attention of the nutritionists and researchers in the field of diet and disease research due to the potential health benefits associated with some of its biologically active components. —ALA, lignan-Secoisolariciresinol diglyco- side (SDG) and dietary fiber. The roots of *L. usitatissimum* contain measurable concentrations of lignans and isoflavones. The growing popularity of flax is due to its potentiality in reducing - cardiovascular diseases, risk of cancer, particularly of the mammary and prostate gland cancer, anti-inflammatory activity, laxative effect, and alleviation of menopausal symptoms and osteoporosis. Flaxseed has new prospects as functional food at present because of consumer's growing interest for food with superb health benefits. It has become an attractive ingredient in the diets specially structured for specific health benefits because of its excellent nutritional profile and promising health benefits. Flaxseed is well-known for the content of chemical compounds with specific biological activity and functional properties like solubility, thermal stability, emulsifying properties and electrostatic charge

density, water holding and fat absorption capacities polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) omega-3 family, soluble dietary fibers, lignin's, proteins and carbohydrates. An analysis of flax averaged 41% fat, 20% protein, 28% total dietary fibre, 7.7% moisture and 3.4% ash, which is the mineral-rich residue left after samples are burned. The protein content of the seed decreases as the oil content increases. Brown and yellow varieties of flaxseed are virtually identical in their nutrient content.

Fig.No1 Flower of L.usitatissimum

The amount of pigment present determines the seed coat colour, a feature that can be changed through normal plant breeding practices. Nutritionists all over the world suggest incorporation of omega 3 fatty acid sources in the diet. Flaxseed serves as the best omega 3 fatty acid source to the non-fish eaters. Edible flaxseed products include the whole flaxseed, ground meal and extracted oil or mucilage. These products have been intended to use as nutritional additives in the preparation of a number of dietary items such as baked cereal products, ready to eat cereals, fiber bars, salad toppings, meat extenders, bread, muffins and spaghetti.

Fig No.2 Seeds L.usitatissimum

Herbal Gel

A gel is a solid or semisolid system of at least two constituents, consisting of a condensed mass enclosing and interpenetrated by a liquid. Gels and jellies are composed of small amount of solids dispersed in relatively large amount of liquid, yet they possess more solid-like than liquid-like character. The characteristic of gel and jelly is the presence of some form of cutaneous structure, which provides solid-like properties. e.g. of herbal gels are Aloe vera herbal gel, Neem herbal gel, cucumber gel for face, Hair gels, Citrus and hibiscus moisture hold gel, Saffron moisture gel, Anti-acne gel, etc. Herbal remedies are getting increasing patient compliance as they are devoid of typical side effects of allopathic medicines. The present research has been undertaken with the aim to formulate and evaluate the herbal gel containing French marigold flower extract. The gel formulation was designed by using Carbapol 940, French marigold flower extract, propylene glycol, methyl paraben, propyl paraben and required amount of distilled water.

Herbal medications are considered safer than allopathic medicines as allopathic medicines are associated with the side effects. One of the methods for its survival is preparation of extract and their formulations for better absorption and penetration of the active moiety into the systemic circulation. Polymer is simply a compound made up of repeating units. Polymers are used to give the structural network which is essential for the preparation of gels. For topical treatment of dermatological disease as well as skin care, a wide variety of vehicles ranging from solids to semisolids and liquid preparations is available to clinicians and patients. Within the major group of semisolid preparations, the use of transparent gels has expanded both in cosmetics and in pharmaceutical preparations. Numbers of medicated products are applied to the skin or mucous membrane that either enhance or restore a

fundamental function of a skin or pharmacologically alter an action in the underlined tissues.

Advantages of Gel

- Non-greasy application
- Being easy to formulate with active ingredients
- Adhering well to the application site
- Being washable and non-toxic
- Stability over time
- Ability to target affected area for rapid treatment and relief
- Preventing unwanted side effects through bypassing the digestive system
- Easy spreading

Disadvantages of Gel

- Some drugs aren't absorbed easily through the skin
- There's a possibility of an allergic reaction
- The effect of gels initiates slower (but lasts longer)
- Additives in the gel may irritate the skin

PLANT PROFILE

Synonyms:

Linum crepitans (Boenn.) Dumort.

Linum humile Mill.

Linum indehiscens (Neilr.) Vavilov & Elladi

II. Phytochemicals and Chemical Constituents

L. usitatissimum contains essential amino acids such as arginine, cysteine, glutamine, histidine and methionine. Methionine is full of phytoestrogen and could powerfully prevent osteoporosis in women after menopause.

It is known to contain oil (40–50%) and meal, comprising of protein (23–34%), ash (4%), viscous fiber/mucilage (5%), and lignan precursors (9–30 mg/g of the defatted meal)

Linolenic acid is a only trienoic acid accounted for > 40% of the total fatty acids, while C12-C16 trienoic fatty acids were not found at different stages of linseed development. Studies suggest

that desaturation/elongation mechanism has no role in developing linolenic acid in linseed. Hexadecatrienoic acid might present at a concentration of <0.005% of the total fatty acids. The investigation showed that in flax seed oil linoleic (31.3± 2.1 mg %) and linolenic (40.2±2.9 mg %) acids were predominant and together constitute principal basic of research composition. The flax seed oil contained also palmitic and stearic acids in less quantities. Linamarin and lotaustralin are two glucosides find in this medicinal plant. A small 69 residue protein, called *L. usitatissimum* trypsin inhibitor (LUTI) was isolated from flax seeds, which belongs to the potato 1 family of serine proteinase inhibitors based on Sequence homology studies. Protein gluten, omega- 3 fatty acid, and lignans are major constituents of Flax seeds. Its phenolic compounds could be used for hormone-dependent oncological diseases due to their antioxidant and phytoestrogenic effects. The major lignan find in flax seeds is, (+)-[2R, 2R]-bis [(4-hydroxy-methoxyphenyl) methyl]-1, 4-butanediyl-bis (-glucopyranoside) or secoisolariciresinol glucoside (SDG), found by 1 – 2% in flax seeds, which is ten to hundred times more lignan than most other edible plants seeds [28, 29]. (SDG) is a valuable food constituent due to its function as a precursor for enterolignans. SDG is considered to have chemopreventive activity against various tumours and cardiovascular disorders. It is reported that flaxseed also contains other lignans like matairesinol, lariciresinol, hinokinin, arctigenin, pinioresinol and demethoxysecoisolariciresinol in small quantity with several phenolic acid compounds. Beside (SDG), flaxseed contains SDG isomer, matairesinol, pingoesinol diglucoside and isolariciresinol. Phenolic acids such as p-coumaric, o- coumaric, ferulic, p-hydroxybenzoic, gentisic, vanilic, sinapic acids in free and /or bound form were reported in flaxseed. Caffeic acid and their glucosides were reported in

the flaxseed as well. Furthermore, flaxseed reported containing phenylpropanoid glucoside; such as linusamarin, linocinamarin and daucosterol along with a variety of flavonoids such as herbacetin 3, 8-Odiglucopyranoside, herbacetin 3, 7-O-dimethyl ether, kaempferol 3, 7-O-diglucopyranoside and herbacetin diglucoside. As mentioned, Flax fibers accumulate components like phenolic acids and flavonoids which showed antioxidant activity. PUFA (ALA) and phytoestrogenic lignans are considered as a source of biologically active components that have been shown to be co-preventive and co-therapeutic in a wide variety of ailments. The maximum lignan concentration in flaxseed is 3% (w/w);. In addition, flaxseed meal is rich in cyanogenic compounds including linamarin, lotaustralin, linustatin, neolinustatin, and amygdalin. Different components of *L. usitatissimum* root were isolated using silica gel column chromatography including vanillic acid, syringic acid, xanthine, vitexin, isovanillin, (E)-3, 3'-dimethoxy-4, 4'-dihydroxystilbene, tachioside, β -sitosterol, and stigmasterol mixture, berberine. After studying on a 70% ethanol extract of flaxseed through a combination of various chromatographic techniques, including silica gel, macroporous adsorbent resin, Sephadex LH-20, and preparative HPLC, some constituents were isolated. On the basis of spectroscopic data analysis, they were elucidated as 1-methylethyl-2-O-beta-D-glucopyranosyl-(1" --> 6')-beta-D-glucopyranoside, linustatin, neolinustatin, lotaustralin, linamarin, deoxyguanosine, deoxyadenosine, (+)-pinoresinol-4'-O-beta-D-glucopyranoside, 4-O-beta-D-glucopyranosylvanillyl alcohol and tachioside (, separately. Drying temperature (40 °C for 8 hrs.), solvents (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (6:1)) and extraction time (continuously extracted for 8 hrs.) are reported as an optimum extraction method for *L. usitatissimum* seed oil. Moreover, acid-base

was reported as the best way of methyl esterification.

III. Chemical structure of flaxseed

The chemical content of the flaxseed varies according to the environmental conditions in which the plant grows and the characteristics of the genotypes. The flaxseeds consist of about 35-45% lipids, 30% dietary fibre, between 20 to 30 % protein, 10% mucilage and glycoside linamarin 5-6% gum. Major lignan present in flaxseed is secoisolariciresinol diglycoside (SDG). The total protein content composed of mainly 80% globulins (linin and conlinin) and 20% glutelin. Flax protein is relatively rich in arginine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid. However, lysine, methionine and cysteine are the limiting amino acids and gluten-free. Flaxseed oil is composed of 73% polyunsaturated fatty acids, 18% monounsaturated fatty acids and 9% saturated fatty acids. It is also the richest known plant source of the omega 3 (n-3) fatty acid, α -linolenic acid (ALA), which comprises 55% of the total fatty acids. Flaxseed oil is mainly found as triacylglycerols (98%) with lower content of phospholipids (0.9 %) and free fatty acids (0.1%). In addition to, cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin are insoluble fiber constituents abundantly found in flaxseed while mucilage gums form is the soluble fiber fraction. Flaxseed is an equally good source of minerals, particularly, phosphorus, magnesium, calcium, iron, zinc and very little amount of sodium. However, 98 hemicellulose and lignin are insoluble fiber constituents abundantly found in flaxseed while mucilage gums form is the soluble fiber fraction. Flaxseed is an equally good source of minerals, particularly, phosphorus, magnesium, calcium, iron, zinc and very little amount of sodium. However, flaxseed contains toxic components such as trypsin, myo-inositol phosphate inhibitors, cadmium, cyanogenic glycosides.

GILOY:

CLASSIFICATION:**Table No.2: Taxonomical classification of Giloy**

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Mangnoliophyta
Class	Mangnoliophyta
Order	Ranunculales
Family	Menispermaceae
Genus	Tinospora
Species	Tcordifolia

Synonyms:*Campylus* Lour.*Fawcettia* F.Muell.*Hypsipodes* Miq.**ii. Chemical Composition**

The chemical constituents of giloy belong to different classes such as glycosides, steroids, polysaccharides, phenolics, aliphatic compounds, alkaloids. Leaves are rich in protein (11.2%), calcium and phosphorus. Stem and root part of *T. cordifolia* contain alkaloids as active constituents. These are tembetarine, magnoflorine, tinosporin, isocolumbin, jatrorrhizine, berberine, aporphine alkaloids, choline, tetrahydropalmatine, palmatine which showed anti-cancer, anti-viral, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetes, immunomodulatory and anti-psychiatric action. Additionally, whole plant of *T. cordifolia* include furanolactone, Lactones, diterpenoid, Cleodrane derivatives [(5R, 10R)-4R-8R-dihydroxy-cleroda-13, 14-dieno-17, 12S:18, 1S-dilactone], columbin tinosporides, jateorine, tinosporin. They contain biological actions such as anti-inflammatory, Vasorelaxant, anti-microbial, anti-viral and anti-hypertensive. Shoot part of *T. cordifolia* contains Steroids (β -sitosterol, Makisterone A, δ -sitosterol, giloinsterol, 20 β -hydroxyecdysone, Ecdysterone). They are effective in glucocorticoid induced osteoporosis in early inflammatory arthritis. They tempt cell cycle arrest in G2/M phase and inhibits TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6 and COX-2 and apoptosis through c-Myc

suppression. Stem of *T. cordifolia* contain Glycosides. Their active constituents are 18-norcleodrane glucoside, Tinocordifolioside, cordifolioside A, B, C, D and E, Furanoid diterpine glucoside, Cordioside, Syringin, pregnane glycoside Syringin-apiosylglycoside, palmatosides. They showed immunomodulation in Parkinson's disease, dementia, motor and cognitive disorder, neurological disorders like ALS. They inhibit NF- κ B to show anti-cancer properties. 35-41 Whole plant of *T. cordifolia* contain aliphatic compounds. The active constituents are Octacosanol, Nanocosanol, 15-one dichloromethane, Heptacosanol. They showed anti-nociceptive and anti-inflammatory activity. They also inhibit TNF- α from binding to the DNA and provide protection against 6-hydroxydopamine induced Parkinsonism in rats. Stem part of *T. cordifolia* contain Sesquiterpenoids and Tinocordifolin which exhibits an antiseptic activity. The other parts of *T. cordifolia* contain active constituents such as Jatrorrhizine, Tinosporic acid, 3-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzyl)-4-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzyl) tetrahydrofuran, N-trans-feruloyltyramine as diacetate, Giloin. They showed a protective effect against HIV (human immunodeficiency virus). The chief Phytoconstituents of *T. cordifolia* are diterpenoid furano lactone, cordifolide, cordifol, heptacosanol, tinosporide, β -sitosterol, tinosporine, clerodane furano diterpine, tinosporaside, and columbin respectively. Alkaloids

such as magniflorine, Berberine, palmatine, nonglycoside giloinin gilosterol, tembertarine, choline and tinosporin has been reported from the stem part of the T.Cordifolia.

Fig No.2: Giloy a natural depository of medicines while superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione (GSH) peroxidase were found to be decreased significantly ($P < 0.01$). Its leaf extract powder showed strong antioxidant activity. Plant also possesses phenolic compounds in stem extract (–) epicatechin has been reported for the first time in Tc stem extract. *Tinospora sinensis* (Lour.) contains BBR that possesses diverse biological activities

- **Antidiabetic Activity**

Tc (Thunb.) Miers possesses phytoconstituents tinosporaside and BBR which show very strong antidiabetic activity. Plant extract or Satva restore and work in both conditions hypoglycemic and hyperglycemic state. Guduchi Churna (GC) and extracted juice, decoction, and GC prepared from its leaves is used to treat diabetes. Tc consumption ameliorates changes in kidney chondroitin sulfate/dermatan sulfate in diabetic rats. Plant possesses nutraceuticals most of them are antidiabetic. Tc stem bio-organic compounds act as inducer and sensitizers of insulin production in pancreatic cells.

- **Antimicrobial Activity**

Tinospora cardifolia (Giloy) extracts were found active against *Streptococcus mutans*, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *staphylococcus aureus* at 2% of concentration with a zone of inhibition of

19 mm. *Tinospora* exhibited antimicrobial activity against *S. mutans*. Tc acetone and ethyl acetate extracts were found active against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas* spp. These have shown a minimum bactericidal concentration values between 1.29 and 22.73 mg/mL. Tc shade dried and powdered leaves showed anti-microbial property against *E. coli*. *Tinospora sagittata* (Oliv.) Gagnep. var. *craveniana* (S.Y.Hu) Lo (TSG) is a traditional Chinese herb. This is used for the treatment of upper respiratory tract infection and has anti-bacterial and anti-ulcer activity. It shows bactericidal effects due to presence of major component, palmatine, against *Helicobacter pylori* SS1 *in vitro* and *in vivo*. PMT derivatives showed antibacterial activities against six metronidazole resistant *H. pylori* strains. It also exhibited a good safety profile with a half-lethal dose (LD50) of over 1000 mg/kg. Tc extracts were found active against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. These showed dose-dependent inhibitory activity with maximum effect of 18–32%.

- **Antiprotozoan Activity**

Tc leaf extract showed good anti-plasmodial activity. *T. crispa*, found in Indonesia is used for the traditional treatment of malaria and Leishmaniasis by local people. It was found highly active against *Plasmodium falciparum* and also against *Babesia divergens* and *Leishmania infantum*. It shows cytotoxicity to sporozoites activity (IC50 values $< 3 \mu\text{g/mL}$). *T. crispa* possessed a broad antimalarial activity. while Tc shows anti-trypanosomiasis, anti-leishmaniasis, and anti-malaria activity. Both plant derivatives including the crude extracts, and bioorganic compounds are used in preparation of anti-leishmanial medicines.[48] Its natural compounds inhibit the cell cycle arrest have proven effective for killing cancer cells *in vitro*. It inhibits the activities of cyclins and cyclin-dependent kinases, as well as other proteins and enzymes involved in proper regulation of cell cycle leading to

controlled cell proliferation. Plant possesses novel antimalarial compounds that could serve as a leads for the development of new and effective antiplasmodial drugs.

- **Antiviral activity**

Hot extract of Tc shows potential antiviral preventive and immunity booster activity against COVID-19. Giloy Ghanvati shows strong therapeutic potential against viral diseases.[52] Tc, BBR can regulate 3CLpro protein's function due to its easy inhibition and thus can control viral replication. These are proved potential drug candidates for COVID-19.[53] More specifically, secondary metabolites were found highly active against SARS-CoV-2. Chemicals in Tc may activate Nrf2, which leads to the overexpression of antioxidant enzymes such as CAT, GSH peroxidase (GPx), GSH-S-transferase (GST), and GSH reductase (GR), and thereby induces the adaptive response to oxidative stress. Tc is also able to reduce NF- κ B signaling by inhibiting PI3K/Akt, activating AMPK and sirtuins, and downregulating PI3K/Akt. It can be used for treatment of gastrointestinal diseases, inflammatory processes, and microbial infections, as immunostimulants, and in chemotherapy [Table 1].[54] Diterpenoids found in spices and herbs play a significant role against viral infections.[27] These are potent compounds found in natural medicines.[55] Tc also contains various classes of alkaloids, lignans, steroids, and terpenoids. Diterpenoids are considered the major active compounds in *T. sinensis* with unique structures and activities.

- **Antibacterial Activity**

Tc shows antibacterial activity against *S. mutans*. Its stem extract was found active against drug resistant *S. aureus*. Its subminimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of AuNPs (50, 100, and 150 μ g/mL) greatly affected the biofilm-forming ability of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Ethanolic extract of Tc showed growth inhibitory potential

Salmonella Typhi (Gram-negative), *S. aureus*, and *Serratia marcescens* (Gram-positive). Tc, and studied the action of AuNPs against *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 biofilm. Solvent extracts of Tc, showed antibacterial potential against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumoniae*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *S. Typhi*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Salmonella Paratyphi*, *Salmonella Typhimurium*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter aerogenes* by disc diffusion method

- **Anti-parasitic Activity**

Amphistome *Gastrothylax crumenifer* parasites with the treatment of medicinal plants Tc.[60] *In vitro* anthelmintic activity of plants have been studied on trematode parasites liver fluke *Fasciola gigantica* tegument of *G. Crumenifer* and on amphistome *Orthocoelium scoliocoelium*, *F. gigantica*, *G. crumenifer* and intestinal helminthes.

- **Anti-Gout Properties**

Nineteen fungal endophytes were isolated from the medicinal plant Tc and evaluated for their XO inhibitory activity. Basically xanthine oxidase inhibition is required to restore hyperuricemic condition and for treatment gout.

- **Analgesic Activity**

Tc extract acts as good analgesics, it significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased the response time and decreased the number of writhes in hot plate method and abdominal writhing. Tc shows peripheral analgesic effect and marked central analgesic effect vis-à-vis standard modern antipyretics.TSY exhibits combined analgesic, sedative, and anti-gastric cancer activities. *In vivo* experiments TSY extract exhibits good analgesic and sedative effects. Polysaccharide rich extract (PRE) isolated from Tc, on the survival of intracellular MTB strains and activation of macrophages, was investigated. PRE treatment up regulated the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL- β , TNF- α , IL-6, IL-12, and IFN- γ in RAW 264.7 cell line. This classical activation of macrophases by PRE treatment and killing of intracellular MTB is due to no induction.

Neem:

Fig No.3 Leaves Of Neem

I. Synonyms:

Antelaea azadirachta (L.) Adelb.
 Antelaea canescens Cels ex Heynh.
 Antelaea javanica Gaertn.
 Azadirachta indica subsp. vartakii Kothari,
 Londhe & N.P.Singh
 Melia azadirachta L.
 Melia fraxinifolia Salisb.
 Melia hasskarlii K.Koch
 Melia indica (A.Juss.) Brandis
 Melia japonica Hassk.
 Melia parviflora Moon
 Melia pinnata Stokes

ii. Taxonomical Classification

Table No. 3: Taxonomical classification

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Order	Sapindales
Family	Meliaceae
Genus	<i>Azadirachta</i>
Species	<i>A. Indica</i>

III. Phytochemicals

The most important active constituent is azadirachtin and the others are nimbolinin, nimbin, nimbidin, nimbidol, sodium nimbinat, gedunin, salannin, and quercetin. Leaves contain ingredients such as nimbin, nimbanene, 6-desacetylnimbinene, nimbandiol, nimbolide, ascorbic acid, n-hexacosanol and amino acid, 7-desacetyl-7-benzoylazadiradione, 7-desacetyl-7-

benzoylgedunin, 17-hydroxyazadiradione, and nimbiol. Quercetin and β -sitosterol, polyphenolic flavonoids, were purified from neem fresh leaves and were known to have antibacterial and antifungal properties, And seeds hold valuable constituents including gedunin and azadirachtin.

IV. Uses

• Anticancer

Cancer is multifactorial disease and major health problem worldwide. The alteration of molecular/genetic pathways plays role in the development and progression of cancer. The treatment module based on allopathic is effective on one side but also shows adverse effect on the normal cell. Earlier studies reported that plants and their constituents show inhibitory effects on the growth of malignant cells via modulation of cellular proliferation, apoptosis, tumour suppressor gene, and various other molecular pathways . Neem contains flavanoids and various other ingredients that play an important role in inhibition of cancer development. Large number of epidemiological studies proposes that high flavonoid intake may be correlated with a decreased risk of cancer.

• Antibacterial Activity:

An examination was performed to survey antimicrobial sufficiency of home grown choices as endodontic irrigants and differentiated and the standard irrigant sodium hypochlorite and result confirmed that leaf concentrates and grape seed extricates demonstrated zones of restriction prescribing that they had antimicrobial properties. Moreover, leaf extract showed fundamentally more remarkable zones of inhibition than 3% sodium hypochlorite. The antibacterial development of guava and neem isolates against 21 strains of food borne pathogens was evaluated and delayed consequence of the examination recommended that guava and neem extracts have compounds containing antibacterial properties that

can possibly be significant to control food borne pathogens and deterioration life forms.

- **Antifungal Activity:**

Investigation was made to assess the adequacy of different concentrates of neem leaf on seed borne parasites *Aspergillus* and *Rhizopus* and results affirmed that development of both the contagious species was fundamentally repressed and controlled with both alcoholic and water extract. Moreover, alcoholic concentrate of neem leaf was best

- **Anti-Inflammatory Effect of Neem:**

Plants or their isolated derivatives are in the practice to treat/act as anti-inflammatory agents. An examination result has affirmed that concentrate of *A. indica* leaves at a dose of 200mg/kg, p. o., demonstrated huge anti-inflammatory activity in cotton pellet granuloma test in rodents.

6. Material and Instruments

a) Instruments used for work

Table no. 4: List of instruments used for work

Sr. No.	Name of Instrument
1	Soxhlet Apparatus
2	Electronic weighting balance
3	pH meter
4	Brookfield viscometer
5	Heating mantle
6	Electronic waterbath

b) Chemicals used for work

Table no. 5: List of chemicals used for work

Sr.no.	Chemicals
1.	Ethanol
2.	Carbopol 934
3.	Propylene glycol
4.	Methyl paraben
5.	Propyl paraben
6.	Triethanolamine
7.	Glycerine
8.	Cetyl alcohol
9.	Distilled water

Extraction

1. Neem:

After gathering and properly cleaning the leaves with distilled water, the leaves were allowed to dry in the shade for a period of ten days. Powdered dried leaf material was created. After mixing 150 ml of 90% ethanol into 100g of powder, it was placed in a percolator and allowed to macerate for seven days, string periodically, after being infused with 350 ml of 90% ethanol for three hours. A residue that was blackish green extract. Airtight containing was used to store the extract in a dark, cold environment.

2. Flax Seed:

Extraction was carried out from 10g powder of flax seed sample in 250ml of Acetone. For this extraction Soxhlet apparatus is used. Extraction was conducted using Acetone. Below Soxhlet, thimble tube is placed in that 10g of sample is placed in packet of Whatmann filter paper. Round bottom flask containing acetone is placed in heating mantle carrying 58 degree Celsius temperature for 2 hrs. Extract which is found is in liquid form, so it is evaporated using Rotavap at 65 degree Celsius. Then heated extract which is obtained is in solid form. It is weighed and stored at room temperature.

3. Giloy:

10g dried powder of Giloy leaves mixed with 100ml Ethanol and then placed for 24 hrs for maceration. After 24 hrs mixture is filtered and filtrate is evaporated at 105 degree Celsius in Hot air oven by putting it in petri dish. Solid extract which is obtained is used as Giloy extract.

Test

i. Test For Saponins

Foam test

A small amount of extract taken in a test tube with little quantity of water. Shake vigorously. Appearance of foam persisting for 10 minutes indicates presence of Saponin.

ii. Test For Alkaloids

a) **Mayer's test:** 2-3 ml of filtrate with few drops of Mayer's reagent gives ppt.

b) **Wagner's test:** 2-3 ml of filtrate with few drops of Wagner's reagent gives

Reddish brown colour.

iii. Test For Tannins

Ferric chloride test

To the alcoholic solution of the extract add few drops of neutral ferric chloride solution. Appearance of green colour indicates presence of Tannins.

iv. Test For Steroids

Liebermann's reaction

Mix 3 ml extract with 3 ml acetic anhydride. Heat and cool. Add few drops of conc. H₂SO₄. Blue color appears.

v. Test For Flavanoids

Alkaline reagent test

Test solution when treated with sodium hydroxide solution shows increase in the intensity of yellow colour which becomes colourless on addition of few drops of dilute acid.

vi. Test For Terpenoids

Salkowski reaction

To 2 ml of extract, add 2 ml chloroform and 2 ml of conc. H₂SO₄. Shake well. Chloroform layer appears red and acid layer shows greenish yellow fluorescence.

vii. Test For Reducing Sugar

Benedict's test

Mix equal volume of Benedict's reagent and test extract in test tube. Heat in boiling water bath for 5 min. Solution appears green, yellow or red depending on amount of reducing sugar present in test solution.

viii. Test For Proteins

Biuret test

a) Add 2ml of Biuret reagent to 2ml of extract. Shake well and warm it on water bath. Appearance of red or violet colour indicates presence of proteins.

b) To 3 ml. extract add 4% NaOH and few drops of 1% CuSO₄ solution. Violate or pink colour appears. ^[2]

9. Preformulation study

Preformulation studies are needed to ensure the development of a stable as well as effective and safe dosage form. It is a stage of development during which the pharmacist characterizes the physic-chemical properties of the drug substances and its interaction with various formulation components. Goals of Preformulation study:

- To determine the necessary physicochemical parameter of a new drug substance.
- To establish its incompatibility with excipients of formulation.

10. Experimental Design

a. Formulation of Herbal Gel

b. Preparation of herbal gel

Method of preparation

- Accurately weighed Carbopol 934 was taken in a beaker and dispersed in 50 ml of distilled water.
- Kept the beaker aside to swell the Carbopol for half an hour and then stirring should be done using mechanical/lab stirrer at 1200 rpm for 30 min.
- Take of propylene glycol and required quantity of Extract.
- Take propylene glycol in another beaker and add weighed quantity of propyl paraben and methyl paraben to it and stirred properly.
- After all, Carbopol dispersed, 1 gm extract and preservatives solutions were added with constant stirring.
- Finally, volume made upto 100 ml by adding remaining distilled water and Triethanolamine was added drop wise to the formulations for adjustment of required skin pH (6.8-7) and to obtain the gel at required consistency. ^[3]
- **Formulation table**

Table no. 5: Formula for Herbal gel

Sr.no.	Ingredients	Batches					Role of ingredient
		A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	
1	Ethanollic extract	1 gm	0.5 gm	1 gm	0.5 gm	1 gm	Therapeutic agent
2	Carbopol 934	0.5 gm	1 gm	1 gm	0.5 gm	0.5 gm	Thickner
3	Propylene glycol	10 ml	Humectant				
4	Methyl paraben	0.2 gm	Preservative				
5	Propyl paraben	0.1 gm	Preservative				
6	Triethanolamine	Qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	Nutralizer
7	Glycerin	1 ml	Vehicle				
8	Distilled water	Upto 100ml	Vehicle				

Evaluation of gel

I. Physical Evaluation

Physical parameters such as color and appearance were evaluated.

II. Homogeneity

All developed gels were tested for homogeneity by visual inspection after the gels have been set in the container for their appearance and presence of any aggregates.

III. pH

The pH of various gel formulations were determined by using digital pH meter. 2.5gm of gel was accurately weighed and dispersed in 25ml of distilled water and stored for two hours. The measurement of pH of each formulation was carried out in triplicate and the average values are represented. The pH of dispersions was measured using pH meter.

IV. Spreadability

Spreadability was determined by the apparatus which consists of a wooden block, which was provided by a pulley at one end. By this method spreadability was measured on the basis of slip and drag characteristics of gels. An excess of gel (about 2 g) under study was placed on this ground slide. The gel was then sandwiched between this slide and another glass slide having the dimension of fixed ground slide and provided with the hook. Weight of 1 kg was placed on the top of the slide

for 5 minutes to expel air and to provide a uniform film of the gel between the slides. Excess of the gel was scrapped off from the edges. The top plate was then subjected to pull of 50 g. With the help of string attached to the hook and the time (in seconds) required by the top slide to cover a distance of 6.5 cm be noted. A shorter interval indicates better spreadability.

Spreadability was calculated using the following formula:

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Where, S = Spreadability,

M = Weight in the pan (tied to the upper slide),

L = Length moved by the glass slide and

T = Time (in sec.) taken to separate the slide completely each other.

V. Viscosity

Viscosity of herbal gel was determined by using Brookfield rotational viscometer at 5, 10 20, 30 and 50 rpm using spindle no.64. Each reading was taken after equilibrium of the sample at the end of two minutes. The viscosity determination of samples was repeated three times.

VI. Stability study

The optimized gel formulations were prepared; packed in aluminum collapsible tubes and subjected to stability studies at 40°C/75% RH for a period of 1 month as per ICH Guidelines. Samples were withdrawn at 1 month time intervals

and evaluated for physical appearance, pH, rheological properties, spreadability.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Extraction of flax seed

Table no. 6: Extractive values of flax seed

Sample	Extraction method	Solvent used	Wt. of sample	Extraction value (%w/w)
<i>Linum usitatism.</i> Seed powder	Soxhlet extraction	Ethanol	30 gm	10% w/w

Preformulation study

Organoleptic Characterization for flower powder

Table no. 7: Organoleptic characteristics of extract

Seed powder	Characteristics
Color	Brown
Odor	Offensive
Taste	Pungent

Table no. 8: Preliminary Phytochemical investigation

Sr. No	Tests	Inference
1.	Froth formation test	Saponins were absent.
2.	Mayer' and Wagner'test	Alkaloid was present.
3..	Ferric Chloride test	Tannin was present.
4.	LiebermannBurchardtest	Steroid was present.
5.	Sodium hydroxidetest.	Flavonoid was present.
7.	Salkowski test.	Terpenoid was present.
8.	Benedict's test	reducing sugar was absent.

Physicochemical evaluation of Gel

Physicochemical evaluation of Gel

I.Physical Appearance

Table no. 8: Physical appearance of gel

Sr. no.	Batch	Color	Appearance
1	A1	Green	Green
2	A2	Light Green	Green
3	A3	Light Green	Green
4	A4	Dark Green	Green
5	A5	Green	Light green

All formulation batches were found to be homogeneous light Yellow gel preparations

Homogeneity

Measurement of pH

The pH values of all prepared formulation ranged from 6-7 which are considered acceptable to avoid the risk of irritation upon application to the skin because adult skin pH is 5.5.

Spreadability

The time in seconds require to separate the two slides was taken as measure of spreadability.

Table no.9: pH and Spreadability of extracts formulation.

Sr. No.	Batch	pH	Spreadability (gm.sm/sec)
1	A1	6.8 /±0.03	16.15/±0.005
2	A2	6.8 /± 0.03	15.40/±0.005
3	A3	7 /± 0.03	15.39/±0.005
4	A4	6.9 /± 0.03	14.96/±0.005
5	A5	6.7 /± 0.03	14.43/±0.005

Viscosity

Viscosity of gel was determined by using Brookfield rotational viscometer at 5, 10, 20, 30, 50 rpm. Each reading was taken after equilibrium of the sample at the end of two minutes. The samples were repeated three times.

Table no. 10: Viscosity value of herbal gel

Sr. No.	rpm	Viscosity (Cps)
1	5	4227 ±0.11
2	10	4137 ±0.43
3	20	3714 ±0.21
4	30	3678 ±0.69
5	50	3665 ±0.58

Stability studies

Accelerated stability studies indicated that the physical appearance, rheological properties, spreadability in the prepared gel remained

unchanged upon storage for 1 month. The pH observed of prepared gel through 1 month storage was in between 6-7. Rheological properties and spreadability was obtained uniformly. Gel formulation was maintaining drug level after 1 month of accelerated stability.

Table no. 11: Stability evaluation of Gel

Evaluation	Batches	
	Initial	After
Physical appearance	Light green	Light green
Homogeneity	Homogeneous	Homogenous
pH	6.8/±0.03	6.9/±0.03
Spreadability	15.40/± 0.005	15.44/± 0.005
Viscosity	3714 ±0.21	3720 ±0.21

CONCLUSION

Gels are getting more popular nowadays because they are more stable & also can approve controlled release than other semisolid preparations like creams, ointments, etc. The gel formation can approve better absorption characteristics & hence increase the bioavailability of the drug. A thorough investigation into stability characteristics of gel formation over extended period of time may provide scope for its therapeutic use for patients. The principle advantage of topical drug delivery lies in targeting the drug action directly to the site of disorder by allowing accumulation of high local drug concentration within the tissue & around it's vicinity for enhanced drug action this is more effective when drugs with short biological half-life, narrow therapeutic window are applied with topical route. The Project work helped in getting better understanding about the herbal drugs & their extractions, isolation the use of traditional folklore medicines, their mechanism of action, adverse drug reaction, evaluation, etc. Pharmacovigilance is a part of healthcare systems worldwide. In present study, it was demonstrated that the developed herbal gel formulation possess significant, therapeutically efficacious, suitable vehicle for drug delivery in low cost but definitely

with high potential. Developed new herbal gel formulation is suitable for mouth ulcer treatment. However, Clinical studies are in pipeline to establish clinical efficacy of prepared herbal gels.

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HOW TO CITE: Purva Jadhav*, Sonal Kumbhar, Polyherbal Gel Formulation For Treatment Of Gout, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2024, Vol 2, Issue 8, 2593-2606. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13220470>